

Results of the ZKI Top Trends Survey of the ZKI Working Group Strategy and Organisation for the Year 2020

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Summary

The Working Group Strategy and Organisation of the ZKI Association conducts an annual survey on the most important topics and focal points of the member institutions. In 2016 the survey was changed to an online survey using LimeSurvey. For the year 2020, the survey was expanded with an additional catalogue of questions on the focus "digitisation". The main catalogue of 12 core questions is standardised each year and consists of free text questions. The answers are categorized and normalised for this analysis.

In this article, the results of the Top Trends Survey 2020 are presented in detail. The list of questions is given in the Annex. The results are supported by the processed raw data at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666386>

[Table of contents: page 25](#)

[List of figures: Page 26](#)

[List of questions: page 26](#)

[Surveys from previous years: page 28](#)

The top trends in 2020 for the ZKI community are:

Figure 1: Relevant top trends and number of mentions; n=47

As a conclusion, the ZKI IT Top Trends Survey 2020 shows a shift of emphasis within the IT centres from rather technical topics to management, communication and digitization aspects. Although many of these topics have been identified earlier, they were not mentioned so frequently in the surveys. The lack of qualified experts on the labour market due to the high employment rate means that more and more tasks are being outsourced to third-party service providers, even for tasks such as basic system administration, network administration or general operations. This is accompanied by increasing demands for outsourcing of project management, the introduction of workflow solutions and the operation of services in the cloud. This situation appears to be intensified by the requirements of digitization, as an increasing number of projects require more and more tasks to be outsourced and a higher level of governance is required for more complex procurement architectures. The transition to new sourcing architectures will be a challenge for IT centres and will require new skills within teams to manage this complexity and to derive systematic approaches.

Introduction and overview

A total of 66 institutions took part in the survey in 2020 - in the previous year 2019, 38 institutions took part. The numerical values of the horizontal diagram axes always show the number of denominations.

The following figures illustrate the type and size of the institutions as well as the roles of the participants

Figure 2: Type of survey participant setup; n=56

Figure 3: Number of students at the survey participants' institution; n=66

Figure 4: Role of survey participants in the university; n=56

The following were mentioned as miscellaneous roles

- *Digitisation Unit of the RZ Management*
- *Head of IT- and Processmanagement and SAP*
- *Digitisation Coordinator*
- *Manager IT & CIO*
- *Team management*
- *CIA and Head of IT*

Not all participants have indicated where their institution is located. The 47 locations mentioned are distributed among the federal states as follows.

Figure 5: Distribution of survey participants among the federal states

In addition, there was one reply each from Austria and Switzerland.

The next question relates to the IT governance model chosen in the institution.

Figure 6: Model of IT governance at the institutions of the survey participants; n=54

The increased number of responses in 2020 will make it easier to investigate in which type of higher education institution and for which size of institution the models are preferably used.

Figure 7: IT governance by size grouped by governance model

Figure 8: IT governance by size grouped by institution size

The following figures show the model of IT governance in relation to the type of institution.

Figure 9: IT governance by institution type grouped by governance model

Figure 10: IT governance of the institutions grouped by institution type

Focus 2020: Digitisation

For the year 2020, one focus topic was set on the area of "digitalisation".

The textual answers in particular contain many interesting references, which is why some of them are reproduced here in extracts. For the complete overview of the responses, please refer to the data annex.

What are the strongest effects of digitisation on the IT centre of your institution?

Selection from the free text answers (for full details see data appendix):

- *Requirements for IT security and data protection continue to increase*
- *Participation in university-wide process development and process implementation*
- *Increased expectations of service quality*
- *Increased need for consulting and support*
- *Increased complexity of tasks*
- *Greater specialisation of professionals required*
- *More services, while the same staffing levels remains the same*
- *More project business*
- *Higher workload for employees*
- *Nebulous expectations regarding (new) IT services for digitisation*
- *Faster accumulation of technical debts*
- *Rising staffing needs and task overflow*

Is there an overarching digitisation strategy at your institution?

Figure 11: Digitization strategy created; n=66

Of the 32 responses for which no digitisation strategy has yet been submitted, 16 comments indicated that this strategy is currently being developed and widely discussed or that the measures are coordinated by the Presidential Board.

Do university management or the management of the research institution, faculties, administration and IT centre share a common view on digitisation?

Figure 12: Common view on digitisation; n=66

Was the IT centre of the university or research institution involved in digitisation projects?

Figure 13: Involvement of IT centre; n=66

The IT centres were mainly involved in the digitisation projects. Nevertheless, there were 11 comments on this question, which further explained the nature of the involvement.

Selection from free text answers (for full details see data appendix):

- *There are three working groups on the digitisation strategy (research, teaching, administration) and only in one (administration) is the IT centre involved*
- *uncontinuous*

- *It depends on the respective project or the person responsible for the project and their view of the IT service (ranging from "they take care of everything and are the central point" to "they only provide the network and the storage")*
- *There is still considerable potential for improvement in initiatives initiated by the political sector and the projects resulting from successful participation in tenders and competitions. Here, the computer centre still too often only learns about the project proposal AFTER it has been accepted.*
- *In principle yes, but mostly too late*

Which stakeholders drive digitisation projects at your university or research institution?

In this text question, the 45 answers reflect the entire spectrum of functions and institutions at a university or research institution.

Selection from free text answers (for full details see data appendix):

- *The Presidium has a staff unit for digitisation*
- *Those responsible for research and teaching*
- *Individual departments of the university administration*
- *Individual faculties*
- *University management, management of central institutions (IT, HR, BiBo)*
- *University management, rectorate, professors*
- *Chancellor for administration, vice-rectors and professors for teaching*
- *Lecturers (improvement of the teaching offers)*
- *Lecturers in their institutes*
- *Computer centre*
- *Administration (legal requirements, improvement of service offerings)*

Changes to the previous year in the top trends

Compared to the previous year, the top trends have changed as follows:

Abbildung 14: Change in the relevance of top trends compared to the previous year

Figure 15 also includes the number of responses that did not answer the question. This allows speculating, for which topics there might be a broad interest and which topics seem more specialized.

The following presentations give an impression of which topics have increased in relevance, remained unchanged or decreased. In addition, the "no answer" illustrates the more specific topics.

Figure 15: Increase in relevance

Figure 16: Unchanged relevance

Figure 17: Decreasing relevance

Figure 18: No answer on relevance

The core questions of the survey in detail

Each year, 12 questions are asked in the survey, which remain the same and are answered as free text. From these texts, topics are derived and normalized, which are then grouped together for this list. The full answers can be found in the data annex.

What top trends do you generally see in the IT sector?

Figure 19: Top trends in general

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Personnel Attacks Process Management 5G Automation Big Data & Analytics edge computing Lack of skilled workers Mobile working	Internet of Things Blockchain

Which top trends are particularly relevant for you?

Figure 20: Top trends with particular relevance

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Process Management Virtualization Agile Organization Attacks Lack of skilled workers IT Service Management	Big Data micro services E-bill Internet of Things

Which legislative regulations do you see as particularly relevant for you next year?

Figure 21: Relevant laws

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Online Access Act	-
Information Security	-

Which topics are you currently working on strategically?

Figure 22: Strategic topics

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Document management Process Management IT Architecture	Emergency Management

What new management tasks are you currently working on?

Figure 23: Management tasks

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
IT governance Communication	Agile methods CIO structure Acquisition of third-party funds Financial Controlling

In which area are external services becoming more important for you?

Abbildung 24: External service providers

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Information Security	-
Cloud	
System support	
Network	

In which areas do you invest more than before?

Figure 25: Areas with more investment

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Cloud	Software development
Campus Management	Big Data
Digitization	HPC

Which technologies are becoming more important for you?

Figure 26: Technologies with increasing importance

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Container	CEPH object memory
Information Security	tiered storage
Web technologies	VDI Virtual Desktop Infrastructure

What new services or technologies are you currently introducing?

Figure 27: Services and technologies in introduction

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Campus Management System Cloud ERP Collaboration platforms Applicant platform E-bill private cloud	CEPH object memory VDI Virtual Desktop Infrastructure

What IT skills would you like to build up in your organisation over the next year?

Figure 28: Capability building in the organisation

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
More stakeholder communication Agility Solution orientation Advisory competence	Change Management

Which employee skills are becoming more important?

Figure 29: Skills whose importance is increasing

Newly added since 2019	No longer included compared to 2019
Cooperation and coordination	-
Documentation	
Agility	
Interdisciplinary cooperation	
Willingness to learn	
IT Service Management	
Software development	

Which employee skills are becoming less important?

Figure 30: Skills that become less important

Directories

Table of contents

- Summary** 1
- Introduction and overview** 2
- Focus 2020: Digitisation**..... 7
 - What are the strongest effects of digitisation on the IT centre of your institution? 7
 - Is there an overarching digitisation strategy at your institution? 7
 - Do university management or the management of the research institution, faculties, administration and IT centre share a common view on digitisation? 8
 - Was the IT centre of the university or research institution involved in digitisation projects? 8
 - Which stakeholders drive digitisation projects at your university or research institution? 9
- Changes to the previous year in the top trends** 10
- The core questions of the survey in detail**..... 13
 - What top trends do you generally see in the IT sector? 13
 - Which top trends are particularly relevant for you?..... 14
 - Which legislative regulations do you see as particularly relevant for you next year? 15
 - Which topics are you currently working on strategically? 16
 - What new management tasks are you currently working on? 17
 - In which area are external services becoming more important for you? 18
 - In which areas do you invest more than before?..... 19
 - Which technologies are becoming more important for you? 20
 - What new services or technologies are you currently introducing? 21
 - What IT skills would you like to build up in your organisation over the next year? 22
 - Which employee skills are becoming more important? 23
 - Which employee skills are becoming less important? 24
- Directories**..... 25
 - List of figures 25
 - List of questions..... 26
- Surveys of previous years..... 28
 - 2019..... 28
 - 2018..... 28

List of figures

- Figure 1: Relevant top trends and number of mentions; n=47 1

Figure 2: Type of survey participant setup; n=56.....	2
Figure 3: Number of students at the survey participants' institution; n=66.....	3
Figure 4: Role of survey participants in the university; n=56.....	3
Figure 5: Distribution of survey participants among the federal states	4
Figure 6: Model of IT governance at the institutions of the survey participants; n=54.....	4
Figure 7: IT governance by size grouped by governance model	5
Figure 8: IT governance by size grouped by institution size.....	5
Figure 9: IT governance by institution type grouped by governance model	6
Figure 10: IT governance of the institutions grouped by institution type	6
Figure 11: Digitization strategy created; n=66	7
Figure 12: Common view on digitisation; n=66.....	8
Figure 13: Involvement of IT centre; n=66	8
Abbildung 14: Change in the relevance of top trends compared to the previous year.....	10
Figure 15: Increase in relevance.....	10
Figure 16: Unchanged relevance	11
Figure 17: Decreasing relevance	11
Figure 18: No answer on relevance.....	12
Figure 19: Top trends in general	13
Figure 20: Top trends with particular relevance	14
Figure 21: Relevant laws.....	15
Figure 22: Strategic topics	16
Figure 23: Management tasks	17
Abbildung 24: External service providers.....	18
Figure 25: Areas with more investment	19
Figure 26: Technologies with increasing importance.....	20
Figure 27: Services and technologies in introduction	21
Figure 28: Capability building in the organisation.....	22
Figure 29: Skills whose importance is increasing	23
Figure 30: Skills that become less important	24

List of questions

1. What type of university are you from?
 - University
 - university of applied sciences
 - Art / Music University
 - Ecclesiastical college
 - dual university
 - State-recognized private university
 - Research institution
 - Miscellaneous
 - No answer
2. What is your role in the organization?
 - CIO
 - Head of an IT department (computer centre)
 - Head of another central institution
 - Other:
 - no answer

3. In which city is your institution located?
4. How many students does your university have?
 - Up to 5,000
 - 5,001 to 15,000
 - 15,001 to 30,000
 - More than 30.000
 - Comment
 - No answer
5. Which organizational model for IT governance is used at your university?
 - Chancellor or Vice President / as CIO
 - CIO with staff function in the presidential staff
 - Head of a central IT department as CIO
 - CIO Panel
 - CIO model is not established
 - Miscellaneous
 - No answer
6. What are the strongest effects of digitisation on the IT centre of your institution?
7. Is there an overarching digitisation strategy at your institution?
 - Yes
 - No. Digitisation is considered separately in individual contexts.
 - No answer
 - Comment
8. Do university management or the management of the research institution, faculties, administration and IT centre share a common view on digitisation?
 - Yes
 - No
 - No answer
 - Comment
9. Was the IT centre of the university or research institution involved in digitisation projects?
 - Yes
 - No
 - No answer
 - Comment
10. Which stakeholders drive digitisation projects at your university or research institution?
11. Please indicate whether, in your opinion, the relevance of the topic has increased, decreased or not changed since last year.
 - Digitization
 - Information Security
 - Research Data Management
 - Cooperations
 - Machine learning
 - Cloud Usage
 - Big Data
 - Micro-Services
 - Human Resources Development
 - E-bill
12. What top trends do you generally see in the IT sector?
13. Which top trends are particularly relevant for you?
14. Which legislative regulations do you see as particularly relevant for you next year?

15. Which topics are you currently working on strategically?
16. What new management tasks are you currently working on?
17. In which area are external services becoming more important for you?
18. In which areas do you invest more than before?
19. Which technologies are becoming more important for you?
20. What new services or technologies are you currently introducing?
21. What IT skills would you like to build up in your organisation over the next year?
22. Which employee skills are becoming more important?
23. Which employee skills are becoming less important?

Surveys of previous years

2019

Survey

<https://zenodo.org/record/2590659>

Data appendix

<https://zenodo.org/record/2590683>

2018

Survey

<https://zenodo.org/record/1196427>

Data appendix

<https://zenodo.org/record/1183499>